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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
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muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

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FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR

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Abstract. The article examines the importance of youth entrepreneurship as one of the key drivers of the country's socio-economic development. An analysis of the prospects for the development of youth entrepreneurship, including in the education sector, is conducted. A strategy is proposed to diversify and improve existing state policies aimed at engaging young people in entrepreneurial activities, as well as to strengthen the legislative and regulatory framework for supporting and developing youth entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: youth; potential; reforms; education; priority tasks; training centers; diversification; state support; youth entrepreneurship.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada yoshlar tadbirkorligining mamlakat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi muhim omillardan biri sifatidagi ahamiyati yoritib berilgan. Yoshlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish istiqbollari, jumladan ta'lim sohasidagi imkoniyatlar tahlil qilingan. Yoshlarni tadbirkorlik faoliyatiga jalb etishga qaratilgan amaldagi davlat siyosatini diversifikatsiyalash va takomillashtirish, shuningdek O'zbekiston Respublikasida yoshlar tadbirkorligini qo'llab-quvvatlashga doir normativ-huquqiy bazani rivojlantirish strategiyasi taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar; salohiyat; islohotlar; ta'lim; ustuvor vazifalar; o'quv markazlari; diversifikatsiya; davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash; yoshlar tadbirkorligi.

Аннотация. В статье раскрывается значение молодёжного предпринимательства как одного из ключевых факторов социально-экономического развития страны. Проведён анализ перспектив развития молодёжного предпринимательства, в том числе в сфере образования. Предложена стратегия диверсификации и совершенствования действующей государственной политики по привлечению молодёжи к предпринимательской деятельности, а также развития нормативно-правовой базы поддержки молодёжного предпринимательства в Республике Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: молодёжь; потенциал; реформы; образование; приоритетные задачи; учебные центры; диверсификация; государственная поддержка; молодёжное предпринимательство.

INTRODUCTION

Today, youth represents a key driving force and a significant potential for the socio-economic development of a country, which necessitates the formation of effective instruments and mechanisms aimed at stimulating and activating young people, as well as directing their activities toward priority areas of development. In this regard, the article places special emphasis on the analysis of the ongoing step-by-step reforms designed to ensure the comprehensive development of youth and their active involvement in entrepreneurial activities.

Youth entrepreneurship is one of the priority areas for the development of small and medium-sized businesses in Uzbekistan. According to the development concept up to 2030, entrepreneurship among young people serves as a foundation for business activity, contributes to the formation and expansion of the middle class, and supports the creation of a sustainable economic system of the state. The establishment of favorable conditions for the development of youth entrepreneurship and the realization of young people's entrepreneurial potential is expected to generate a significant socio-economic effect.

Particular attention is currently given to the development of youth entrepreneurship, as individuals under the age of 30 constitute approximately 60% of the population of Uzbekistan and represent the core of the country's labor force. Consequently, youth act as a decisive factor in the future socio-economic development of the state. In this context, effective instruments are being introduced to attract young people to entrepreneurial activity, including measures aimed at developing their potential, providing modern professional skills, creating preferential conditions, financial support mechanisms, platforms, and ready-made business models for launching their own enterprises.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, large-scale and systematic reforms are being implemented to increase employment, improve living standards, and stimulate economic growth by actively engaging young people in entrepreneurship and creating new opportunities for conducting competitive business activities. Young people are the most dynamic segment of society, capable of quickly responding to changes and effectively adopting progressive practices. As a result, they possess greater potential and adaptability for entrepreneurial activity compared to other age groups.

An analysis of youth entrepreneurship demonstrates its growing importance and necessity for socio-economic development. The expansion of youth entrepreneurship contributes to the achievement of priority objectives outlined in the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2026–2030, including increasing employment through the creation of new jobs, reducing unemployment and poverty by expanding access to higher-paying occupations, promoting labor mobility and expanding its geographical scope, developing tourism, introducing innovative technologies, producing competitive goods, and ensuring sustainable GDP growth. These outcomes indicate the effectiveness of the reforms being implemented and highlight the need for further improvement of mechanisms aimed at attracting, training, and stimulating youth entrepreneurship in the country.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurial activity among young people and issues related to its regulation are attracting increasing attention from the scientific community. Contemporary research primarily focuses on the following aspects:

entrepreneurship as a social phenomenon, youth entrepreneurship and its specific characteristics, regional dimensions of youth entrepreneurship, social and psychological factors influencing entrepreneurial behavior, and legal mechanisms for protecting entrepreneurial activity.

Issues related to youth and youth entrepreneurship are widely discussed in the works of numerous scholars. General problems of youth sociology are addressed in the studies of Abdullaeva I. M. [1], Ilyinsky I. M. [2], Rupasov E. G. and Ruchkin B. A. [3], Mosyakin I. A. [4], Rakovskaya O. A. [5], Lisovsky V. T. [6], Kukhtevich T. N. [7], among others. Specialized research examining the significance of youth entrepreneurship development and the necessity of its regulation has been conducted by Ruchkina B. A., Saraliev Z. Kh., and Petrova T. E. [8], Golovacheva B. V. [9], Babaeva L. V. and Chirikova A. E. [10], Dryakhlova N. I., Davydenko V. A., Perepelkina O. V., and other scholars.

The economic dimensions of youth entrepreneurship are reflected in the works of Gorfinkel V. Ya. and Shvandar V. A., Zlobin B. K., Kushlin V. I., Rummyantsev A. F., Kotler F. [11], Kotilko V. and Orlova D. [12], Savchenko V. [13], Garankina L. [14], Shulus A., Garadzha M., and others. Various aspects of social governance and regulatory mechanisms for youth entrepreneurship are examined in the studies of N. S. Danakin, L. Ya. Dyatchenko, V. N. Ivanov, G. A. Kotelnikov, and V. I. Patrushev.

Regional aspects of youth entrepreneurship have also been investigated in a number of studies. In particular, the works of Belgorod researchers devoted to the development of youth entrepreneurship and state youth policy play a significant role in advancing this research area, including studies by V. P. Babintsev [15], T. B. Berdnikova [16], V. M. Zakharov [17], Yu. V. Kovrizhnykh [18], and V. V. Ovchinnikov [19].

Despite the substantial number of studies devoted to individual aspects of youth entrepreneurship, relatively limited attention has been paid to its social conditions, performance indicators, and the effectiveness of regulatory mechanisms. An assessment of the relevance of the topic and the degree of its scientific development makes it possible to identify the core research problem, which lies in the contradiction between the objective need to develop youth entrepreneurship and the diverse interests and aspirations of young people on the one hand, and the insufficient effectiveness of existing regulatory mechanisms on the other hand.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a mixed-methods approach to analyze the development of youth entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, with particular emphasis on the education sector. Both qualitative and quantitative research methods were applied to assess the current state, key challenges, and future prospects of youth entrepreneurial activity.

Quantitative methods included the collection and analysis of statistical data from national and regional databases, covering demographic indicators, labor market participation, youth employment levels, and the number of newly established youth-led enterprises. These data made it possible to identify the scale, dynamics, and sectoral structure of youth entrepreneurship, as well as to assess its socio-economic impact.

Qualitative methods comprised a systematic review and synthesis of academic literature, policy documents, and case studies of successful youth entrepreneurial initiatives. In addition, expert interviews and surveys were conducted with young entrepreneurs, managers of training centers, and representatives of public authorities. This approach enabled the identification of key motivational factors, institutional barriers, and conditions influencing youth engagement in entrepreneurial activity.

The research also employed comparative and systemic analysis to examine international best practices and assess their adaptability to the Uzbek socio-economic context. Scenario-based and strategic analysis methods were used to develop proposals aimed at diversification, improvement of public policy, and the formation of effective support mechanisms for youth entrepreneurship.

Overall, the applied methodology provides a comprehensive understanding of youth entrepreneurship by integrating statistical evidence, policy analysis, and practical experience, thereby creating a solid empirical and analytical basis for formulating recommendations on the development of youth entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of youth entrepreneurial activity indicates that young people most frequently choose such areas as information technologies, trade, and education. In particular, youth entrepreneurship in the education sector has demonstrated significant socio-economic relevance, as young entrepreneurs tend to focus on fields aligned with their professional interests and competencies. The establishment of private training centers contributes to socio-economic development by creating new jobs, reducing unemployment, increasing youth interest in career advancement, generating additional budget revenues, and improving the quality of educational services through competition and continuous improvement of teaching standards.

From an economic perspective, training centers also support the development of existing enterprises by enhancing the professional competencies of employees, particularly in foreign language proficiency. This, in turn, facilitates access to international partners and investors, expands sales markets, and strengthens the competitiveness of businesses. From a social standpoint, training centers contribute to raising the cultural and intellectual level of the population, increasing interest in quality education and international employment opportunities, fostering intercultural awareness, and promoting the formation of a socially active and educated generation.

In Uzbekistan, youth represent a substantial potential influencing the country's socio-economic development. A distinctive feature of youth entrepreneurship is its capacity to generate new directions of development, implement innovative solutions, and create original business models. In this context, it is essential to establish an entrepreneurial environment, culture, and infrastructure aimed at consistent and systematic support for youth entrepreneurship. Such support should include not only entrepreneurial education and access to preferential financial resources, but also the development of a comprehensive electronic information and guidance system.

This system should incorporate the legislative and regulatory framework governing entrepreneurial activity, step-by-step guidelines for addressing typical business situations—such as business registration, accounting, and reporting procedures—as well as ready-made business plans applicable to various sectors of the economy. The primary objective of the institutional and regulatory infrastructure is to create favorable conditions for youth entrepreneurship by enabling young people to realize their creative potential, skills, and professional aspirations.

Youth entrepreneurs often seek to differentiate themselves through innovative and creative ideas, which allows them to introduce new solutions more readily, sometimes underestimating the risks associated with entrepreneurial activity. Therefore, timely support for creativity and innovation among young entrepreneurs requires particular attention, including training in risk identification, assessment, and management. The key objective in this regard is to prevent entrepreneurial failure and ensure sustainable business development.

The expansion of youth entrepreneurship contributes to employment growth and the creation of additional job opportunities. Statistical analysis of newly established enterprises indicates that young people predominantly choose the service sector. To maintain sectoral balance and align entrepreneurial activity with national development priorities, it is advisable to guide youth entrepreneurs toward strategically important industries. This can be effectively achieved through specialized training programs and courses that provide relevant skills and competencies aligned with national socio-economic objectives, including sustainable development, education, healthcare, and poverty reduction.

In summary, youth entrepreneurship represents a powerful driver of economic growth and social transformation when supported by a favorable institutional environment and effective policy mechanisms. By empowering young people, fostering innovation, and providing targeted support, youth entrepreneurship can contribute to economic resilience, social progress, and the long-term development of the country, creating a solid foundation for future generations of entrepreneurs.

To assess the prospects for the development of youth entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, it is first necessary to evaluate its demographic and economic scale. Uzbekistan is a densely populated country with a population exceeding 37 million people in 2024, having recorded an annual growth rate of 2.1 % in 2023. Since 2010, the population has increased by more than 8 million people and, according to demographic projections, is expected to reach 43.6 million by 2035.

As of September 1, 2024, the number of young people aged 16–35 amounted to 9,845,036 persons, accounting for approximately 26 % of the total population. This demographic structure highlights the substantial role of youth as a key labor, entrepreneurial, and innovative resource, directly influencing the country's socio-economic development (Table 1).

Table 1. Population Aged 16–35 Years and Labor Market Indicators in Uzbekistan

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Total population, thousand persons	33,905.2	34,558.9	35,271.3	36,024.9	37,799.8
Including age groups, persons:					
16–17	1,017,881	1,027,650	1,052,804	1,069,585	1,147,865
18–19	1,010,789	1,018,627	1,015,964	1,025,936	1,050,788
20–24	2,890,718	2,758,841	2,645,262	2,580,680	2,543,972
25–29	3,212,525	3,218,218	3,157,107	3,081,029	2,969,454
30–35	3,037,479	3,081,371	3,130,537	3,163,221	3,183,745
Labor resources (LR), thousand persons	19,158.2	19,334.9	19,517.5	19,739.6	19,850.1
Employed (E), thousand persons	13,236.4	13,538.9	13,706.2	14,014.2	—
Employment rate, %	66.0	67.0	67.2	67.9	—
Economically active population, thousand persons	14,797.4	14,980.7	15,038.9	15,038.3	—
Economic activity rate, %	73.8	74.1	73.7	72.9	—
Economically inactive population (EIP), thousand persons	4,360.8	4,354.2	4,478.6	4,701.3	—
Unemployed (U), thousand persons	1,561.0	1,441.8	1,332.7	1,024.1	—

The table demonstrates a steady growth of the population of Uzbekistan, which implies a corresponding expansion of the potential consumer base. Currently, 56.4 % of the population is of working age, indicating a substantial labor and entrepreneurial resource. Each year, approximately 600–700 thousand young people enter the labor market. Of this number, around 150–200 thousand enroll in bachelor's degree programs, about 300 thousand find employment, while nearly 200 thousand begin independent job searches, including opportunities abroad. Under these conditions, the development of organized labor migration represents one of the effective instruments for balancing the labor market and ensuring productive employment.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of April 1, 2024, an analysis of the permanent population structure by gender and age groups (up to 65 years in five-year intervals, and 65 years and older as a single group) indicates that among men, the largest cohort consists of children under four years of age, totaling 2,262.7 thousand persons. The smallest male age group comprises individuals aged 60–64, amounting to 657.0 thousand persons. Among women, the highest number is also observed among girls under four years of age, at 2,108.1 thousand persons, while the lowest number of women is recorded in the 60–64 age group, totaling 736.0 thousand persons. This demographic structure reflects a young population profile, which creates favorable long-term conditions for labor market renewal and entrepreneurial development.

As of April 1, 2024, the population density in Uzbekistan reached 82.3 persons per square kilometer, which is 1.7 persons higher than in the corresponding period of 2023 (80.6 persons per square kilometer as of April 1, 2023). Regional analysis reveals significant territorial differentiation. The highest population density was recorded in Tashkent city, with 6,826.7 persons per square kilometer, followed by Andijan region with 792.8, and Fergana region with 603.5 persons per square kilometer. In contrast, the lowest population density was observed in Navoi region at 9.7 persons, and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan at 12.1 persons per square kilometer. These disparities highlight the importance of region-specific policies aimed at supporting employment, entrepreneurship, and balanced socio-economic development across the country (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Population Density¹

The largest permanent population by region is observed in Samarkand region (4,227.3 thousand people), Fergana region (4,079.5 thousand people), and Kashkadarya region (3,577.0 thousand people). In contrast, the lowest population levels are recorded in Syrdarya region (917.9 thousand people), Navoi region (1,079.9 thousand people), and Jizzakh region (1,514.5 thousand people).

The share of the permanent population is highest in Samarkand region (11.4 %), Fergana region (11.0 %), Kashkadarya region (9.7 %), Andijan region (9.2 %), and Namangan region (8.3 %). At the same time, the lowest shares of permanent population are observed in Syrdarya region (2.5 %), Navoi region (2.9 %), Jizzakh region (4.1 %), Khorezm region (5.4 %), and the Republic of Karakalpakstan (5.4 %). These regional disparities highlight the uneven spatial distribution of human resources and the necessity of differentiated regional employment and entrepreneurship policies.

In search of employment opportunities, a significant proportion of young people migrate to foreign countries. According to the Agency for External Labor Migration of Uzbekistan, as of December 2023, nearly 2 million Uzbek labor migrants were officially registered. Of this total, approximately 1.2 million (60 %) were employed in Russia, 191.8 thousand (10 %) in Kazakhstan, 113.8 thousand (6 %) in Turkey, 68.1 thousand (3 %) in South Korea, while the remaining 424.4 thousand (21 %) were distributed among other countries.

The statistical data indicate that Russia and Kazakhstan remain the primary destinations for Uzbek labor migrants, largely due to widespread knowledge of the Russian language. At the same time, there are significant untapped opportunities for vocational training and employment in other countries. Consequently, labor migration policy continues to play an important role as an instrument for supporting youth employment. Uzbekistan has concluded a number of bilateral labor agreements with major destination countries, including Russia (since 2009) and Kazakhstan (since 2021), as well as agreements with nearly 300 employers in 28 countries, including South Korea, Japan, Turkey, the United Kingdom, and Qatar.

Uzbekistan is actively pursuing a policy aimed at diversifying labor migration destinations and improving working conditions and legal protection for its citizens abroad. In 2023, the Agency for Foreign Labor Activity under the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction facilitated employment for more than 38,000 migrants through organized recruitment programs, primarily in Russia, South Korea, the United Kingdom, and Kazakhstan. For 2024, South Korea allocated a quota of 37,000 Uzbek workers out of 100,000 applicants, and by the end of 2023, the Uzbek diaspora in South Korea reached 87.6 thousand people. In the European Union in 2023, a total of 18,932 work permits were issued to Uzbek citizens, including 6,860 in Poland and 7,546 in Lithuania. These figures demonstrate that employment opportunities for Uzbek youth extend beyond neighboring countries and encompass a broader global labor market.

¹ Stut.uz

One of the main constraints limiting youth employment abroad remains the insufficient level of foreign language proficiency. This factor underscores the growing importance of developing language training centers. An additional justification for such centers is the increasing number of Uzbek students studying abroad. At present, Uzbekistan ranks third globally in terms of the number of students enrolled in foreign higher education institutions. China and India occupy the first and second positions, with 1.05 million and 621.6 thousand students abroad, respectively.

Top 10 countries by number of students studying abroad include:

- China – 1,052.3 thousand students;
- India – 621.6 thousand;
- Uzbekistan – 150.5 thousand;
- Vietnam – 134.1 thousand;
- Germany – 126.2 thousand;
- United States – 115.0 thousand;
- France – 113.5 thousand;
- Saudi Arabia – 105.0 thousand.

Accordingly, the primary objective of establishing language training centers is to provide young people with professional-level proficiency in major foreign languages, thereby contributing to effective intercultural communication, facilitating adaptation and employment abroad, enabling access to higher-paid occupations rather than low-skilled labor positions, and supporting the diversification of labor migration destinations.

In this context, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of Uzbekistan is implementing large-scale initiatives to develop a nationwide network of training and adaptation centers. These centers aim to equip citizens with in-demand professional skills and provide pre-departure training, including language instruction and familiarization with the cultural and historical characteristics of destination countries, thereby enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of temporary labor migration.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

An analysis of the demand for foreign language proficiency among young people reveals several key drivers shaping this trend. First, a significant motivating factor is the increasing mobility of the population, including departure from the Republic of Uzbekistan for the purposes of education, employment, labor migration, and tourism. According to official statistics, the number of citizens of Uzbekistan who left the country for tourism purposes during January–March 2024 amounted to 1,263.0 thousand people. Moreover, in 2024, compared to 2023, the number of citizens traveling to CIS countries increased by 37.8 %, while the number of tourists traveling to non-CIS countries grew by 58.8 %.

These trends indicate a steady expansion of international interaction and highlight the growing importance of foreign language skills as a prerequisite for successful education, employment, and social integration abroad. Consequently, strengthening foreign language education among youth should be regarded not only as a response to migration and mobility processes, but also as a strategic instrument for enhancing human capital, improving employability, and supporting sustainable socio-economic development (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – The Number of Citizens of Uzbekistan Who Left the Republic in January–March 2024²

² Stut.uz

In addition to migration-related factors, two other important drivers of foreign language demand among young people can be identified: the development of entrepreneurship and the development of tourism in Uzbekistan. As the analysis indicates, the most popular foreign languages among young people are Russian, Turkish, Chinese, and French. This growing demand creates additional opportunities for the development of youth entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, particularly in the field of educational services.

An analysis of the activities of language training centers confirms the relevance and effectiveness of this type of entrepreneurial activity. In this context, it is appropriate to apply a language diversification strategy, which involves the introduction of new languages into educational programs and the provision of a wide range of language-learning services tailored to different levels of learner preparedness.

Diversification is a business strategy aimed at expanding activities through the introduction of new products or services or by entering new markets. It helps reduce risks associated with dependence on a single source of income or a single business model. In the context of language training centers, language diversification is an effective strategy for increasing profitability and expanding the client base. This approach involves the development of specialized courses for each language, designed in accordance with specific learning objectives.

The management of a training center should develop a language diversification strategy based on an analysis of learners' goals. Examples include "Chinese for Business," "Turkish for Career Development," "French for Travel," and "Russian for Professional Communication." Educational programs may include intensive courses in two main directions: short-term courses for tourism purposes aimed at rapid language acquisition, and long-term professional courses designed for in-depth language study.

The language diversification strategy includes both horizontal and vertical diversification. Horizontal diversification focuses on expanding the range of languages offered, while vertical diversification involves differentiating courses according to levels of language proficiency (Table 2).

Table 2. Horizontal and Vertical Diversification of Language Training Programs

Level	English	Turkish	Chinese	Russian	Level
A2 B2	Conversational (Tourism, Leisure). Learners understand sentences and frequently used expressions related to areas of immediate relevance (e.g., basic personal and family information, shopping, job search). They can perform tasks requiring a simple exchange of information on familiar topics and describe personal background and everyday matters in simple terms.				Conversational (Tourism, Leisure).
	For Employment, Entrepreneurship Development, and Cooperation. Learners can understand the main ideas of complex texts on both abstract and concrete topics, including technical content. They can communicate fluently and spontaneously with native speakers and produce clear, detailed texts on a wide range of subjects, expressing and justifying opinions.				For Employment and Business Cooperation.
C2	Professional Level for Work and Study. Business English.				Business Turkish.
	Learners are prepared for examinations, academic writing, research papers, textbooks, business correspondence, business trips, conference participation, and partner search. They understand virtually all spoken and written language, can synthesize information from multiple sources, and express themselves fluently, precisely, and spontaneously, conveying subtle shades of meaning.				
Level A2 B2	English				Turkish
	Conversational (Tourism, Leisure). Learners understand sentences and frequently used expressions related to areas of immediate relevance (e.g., basic personal and family information, shopping, job search). They can perform tasks requiring a simple exchange of information on familiar topics and describe personal background and everyday matters in simple terms.	Conversational (Tourism, Leisure).	Conversational (Tourism, Leisure).	Conversational (Tourism, Leisure).	
	For Employment, Entrepreneurship Development, and Cooperation. Learners can understand the main ideas of complex texts on both abstract and concrete topics, including technical content. They can communicate fluently and spontaneously with native speakers and produce clear, detailed texts on a wide range of subjects, expressing and justifying opinions.				For Employment and Business Cooperation.

Horizontal and Vertical Diversification in Youth Entrepreneurship

Horizontal diversification involves expanding an existing range of products or services or entering new geographic markets in which the company already possesses experience and institutional knowledge. In the context of a training center, horizontal diversification implies broadening the portfolio of educational services by introducing new foreign languages—such as Turkish, Chinese, and Russian—in addition to the existing English language courses. This type of diversification allows the training center to respond to diverse educational needs and interests, thereby expanding its target audience and increasing overall demand for its services.

Vertical diversification refers to the expansion of activities across different stages of the value chain. For a training center, this approach may be implemented through the development of multi-level language courses that vary in complexity, such as “Basic,” “Intermediate,” and “Advanced” levels. This structure ensures accessibility of educational services for learners with different levels of prior preparation, ranging from beginners to advanced students, and contributes to the expansion of the client base and the diversification of service offerings.

The introduction of an intermediate level plays a particularly important role, as it supports students who have completed a basic course but are not yet prepared for advanced instruction. In addition, the incorporation of various learning formats—such as online classes, practical training sessions, and short-term internships or workshops conducted with instructors—enhances flexibility and creates additional opportunities for personalized learning pathways.

The implementation of horizontal and vertical diversification strategies enables training centers to better structure and present their services, taking into account the heterogeneous needs, objectives, and competencies of learners. To support this process, it is advisable to conduct trial lessons, launch targeted marketing campaigns, and offer free introductory classes in newly introduced languages. Such measures increase visibility, attract potential clients, and allow learners to familiarize themselves with teaching methodologies and instructors.

To further reduce the risk of declining demand for educational services, training centers may diversify not only language programs but also related academic subjects. For example, preparatory courses in chemistry and biology may be offered for applicants to medical institutions; mathematics, geometry, and physics for engineering-oriented applicants; and literature and history for future philologists. This form of diversification can be effectively implemented through an expansion strategy, which involves extending entrepreneurial activity by adding new educational programs and establishing additional branches. The primary objective of this approach is to enhance operational efficiency and strengthen market competitiveness.

At the same time, the recognition of youth entrepreneurship as a distinct category necessitates the development of a clear and effective legislative and regulatory framework for its management, regulation, and organization. A key initial step in this process is the clarification of the concept of “youth entrepreneurship.” At present, the criteria defining this category remain insufficiently specified. Existing definitions generally classify youth entrepreneurship as entrepreneurial activity carried out by individuals aged 16–30 years, either without forming a legal entity or within legal entities founded by young citizens. However, such definitions do not clarify whether age requirements apply to the entire workforce, a portion of employees, or only the management, nor do they address the role of prior professional experience.

To eliminate ambiguity and ensure consistency in policy implementation, it is necessary to establish a precise definition and a comprehensive set of criteria for youth entrepreneurship. These criteria should encompass not only age limits, but also the duration of entrepreneurial activity and the level of professional education of participants.

In this regard, it appears appropriate to define youth entrepreneurship as entrepreneurial activity carried out by individuals or legal entities that are newly established in a given field and have operated in the market for no more than five years, provided that at least 90 % of the organization’s employees are between the ages of 16 and 30.

Based on this approach, the main criteria for youth entrepreneurship may be formulated as follows:

1. Age criterion: 100 % of employees are aged 16–30, regardless of the sector of activity;
2. Time criterion: the period of operation in the market does not exceed five years;
3. Educational criterion: employees possess at least a bachelor’s degree in the relevant field of specialization.

The absence of a clear legislative definition of youth entrepreneurship currently complicates the identification of its subjects for statistical accounting and analytical purposes. This limitation, in turn, hinders an objective assessment of the effectiveness of legislative and executive measures aimed at supporting youth entrepreneurship. Establishing clear and transparent criteria would therefore contribute to more effective policy design, monitoring, and evaluation, while creating favorable conditions for the sustainable development of youth entrepreneurship.

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